

IKKI NOMA'LUMLI TENGLAMALAR SISTEMALARINI YECHISHDA SIMMETRIK KO'PHADLARDAN FOYDALANISH

Ummatova Mahbuba Axmedovna¹, Karimova Azizaxon Nozimjon qizi²

¹katta o'qituvchi, QDU, ²QDU talabasi

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada simmetrik ko'phadlar va simmetrik ko'phadlarning alohida sinfi bo'lgan darajali yig'indilar hamda ularning elementar matematikaga, xususan, ikki noma'lumli ba'zi tenglamalar sistemasini yechishga tatbiqlari ko'rib chiqilgan.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются симметричные многочлены и степенные суммы (специальный класс симметричных многочленов) и их приложения к элементарной математике, в частности, к решению некоторых систем уравнений с двумя неизвестными.

Annotation. This article examines symmetric polynomials and a special class of symmetric polynomials, called degree sums, and their applications to elementary mathematics, in particular, to solving certain systems of equations in two unknowns.

Kalit so'zlar: simmetrik ko'phadlar, darajali yig'indilar, ikki noma'lumli tenglamalar sistemasi, yechimlar.

Ключевые слова: симметричные многочлены, степенные суммы, системы уравнений с двумя неизвестными, решения.

Keywords: symmetric polynomials, power sums, system of equations in two unknowns, solutions.

Ko'p noma'lumli ko'phadlarni o'rganganda amaliyotda ko'plab tatbiqlarga ega bo'lgan simmetrik ko'phadlarning alohida jihatlarini tahlil etish va buni masalalarda ko'rsatish matematikaning yana bir jozibador qirrasini o'rganuvchilarga yetkazish – fanning, algebraning o'qitilishida muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Ushbu maqolada simmetrik ko'phadlarning maktab matematika kursidagi ikki noma'lumli ba'zi tenglamalar sistemasini osongina yechishga doir tatbiqlarini ko'ramiz.

Ta'rif. Agar ko'p noma'lumli ko'phaddagi ixtiyoriy ikkita noma'lumning o'rinlarini almashtirganda ko'phad o'zgarmasa, u holda bunday ko'phad simmetrik ko'phad deyiladi.

Misol.

$$f(x_1, x_2, x_3) = x_1^2 x_2 x_3 + x_1 x_2^2 x_3 + x_1 x_2 x_3^2$$

ko'phad simmetrik ko'phaddir, chunki bu ko'phaddagi x_1, x_2, x_3 noma'lumlarning hamma 6 ta o'rinlarini almashtirib chiqsak, ko'phad o'zgarmaydi. Chunonchi, x_1 va x_2 noma'lumlarni bir-biri bilan almashtirsak,

$$x_2^2 x_1 x_3 + x_2 x_1 x_3^2 + x_2 x_1 x_3^2$$

ko'phad hosil bo'lib, bu esa berilgan ko'phadning o'zginasidir. Shunga o'xshash, x_2 va x_3 ni almashtirib,

$$x_1^2 x_3 x_2 + x_1 x_3 x_2^2 + x_1 x_3 x_2^2$$

ko'phadni hosil qilamiz, bu esa yana berilgan ko'phadning o'zidir.

n ta noma'lumli simmetrik ko'phadlarning algebraik yig'indisi yana n ta noma'lumli simmetrik ko'phadlar bo'ladi. Haqiqatan ham, noma'lumlarning istalgan o'rin almashtirishida har qaysi simmetrik ko'phad o'zgarib, ravshanki, ularning algebraik yig'indisi va ko'paytmasi ham o'zgarmaydi. Masalan,

$$f_1(x_1, x_2, x_3) = x_1 + x_2 + x_3 \quad \text{va} \quad f_2(x_1, x_2, x_3) = x_1 x_2 x_3$$

simmetrik ko'phadlarning quyidagi algebraik yig'indisi va ko'paytmasi yana simmetrik ko'phadlardir:

$$f_1 \pm f_2 = x_1 + x_2 + x_3 \pm x_1 x_2 x_3;$$

$$f_1 \cdot f_2 = x_1^2 x_2 x_3 + x_1 x_2^2 x_3 + x_1 x_2 x_3^2$$

Ta'rif. x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n noma'lumlardan tuzilgan

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_1 &= x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n, \\ \tau_2 &= x_1 x_2 + x_1 x_3 + \dots + x_{n-1} x_n, \\ &\dots \dots \dots \\ \tau_n &= x_1 x_2 \dots x_n \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

simmetrik ko'phadlar asosiy (elementar) simmetrik ko'phadlar deb ataladi.

Darajali yig'indilar, ya'ni $S_k = x^k + y^k$, $k=1, 2, \dots$ larni $\sigma_1 = x+y$, $\sigma_2 = xy$ lar orqali ifodalovchi keltirib chiqarilgan formulalarni jadval sifatida keltiramiz:

$S_k = x^k + y^k$ larni $\sigma_1 = x+y$, $\sigma_2 = xy$ lar orqali ifodalash
$S_1 = x + y = \sigma_1$
$S_2 = x^2 + y^2 = \sigma_1^2 - 2\sigma_2$
$S_3 = x^3 + y^3 = \sigma_1^3 - 3\sigma_1\sigma_2$
$S_4 = x^4 + y^4 = \sigma_1^4 - 4\sigma_1^2\sigma_2 + 2\sigma_2^2$
$S_5 = x^5 + y^5 = \sigma_1^5 - 5\sigma_1^3\sigma_2 + 5\sigma_1\sigma_2^2$
$S_6 = x^6 + y^6 = \sigma_1^6 - 6\sigma_1^4\sigma_2 + 9\sigma_1^2\sigma_2^2 - 2\sigma_2^3$
$S_7 = x^7 + y^7 = \sigma_1^7 - 7\sigma_1^5\sigma_2 + 14\sigma_1^3\sigma_2^2 - 7\sigma_1\sigma_2^3$

Quyida tenglamalar sistemasini yechishda ushbu teoremdan foydalanish foydadan holi emas.

TEOREMA. Ixtiyoriy α va β sonlar uchun

$$u^2 - \alpha u + \beta = 0 \quad (4)$$

tenglama va
$$\begin{cases} x + y = \alpha \\ xy = \beta \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

ikki noma'lumli tenglamalar sistemasi yechimlari orasida quyidagi bog'lanish mavjud. Agar u_1, u_2 (4) tenglamaning yechimi bo'lsa, (5) tenglamalar sistemasi 2 ta yechimga ega:

$$\begin{cases} x_1 = u_1 \\ y_1 = u_2 \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} x_2 = u_2 \\ y_2 = u_1 \end{cases}$$

aksincha, agar $x = \alpha$, $y = \beta$ (5) sistemaning yechimi bo'lsa, a va b lar (4) kvadrat tenglamaning yechimlari bo'ladi. Bu teoremaning isboti maktab kursidan ma'lum.

1. Yuqoridagi jadval va teoremdan foydalanib, maktab matematika kursidagi ikki noma'lumli ba'zi tenglamalar sistemasini osongina yechish mumkin.

$$\text{1-misol: } \begin{cases} x^3 + y^3 = 65 \\ x + y = 5 \end{cases}$$

tenglamalar sistemasini yeching.

$$\Delta\sigma_1 = x+y, \sigma_2 = xy \text{ deb 1-jadvaldan } S_3 = x^3 + y^3 = \sigma_1^3 - 3\sigma_1\sigma_2$$

Tenglikni e'tiborga olsak, berilgan sistemadan

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_1^3 - 3\sigma_1\sigma_2 = 65 \\ \sigma_1 = 5 \end{cases}$$

tenglamalar sistemasiga ega bo'lamiz. Bundan $\sigma_1 = 5$, $\sigma_2 = 4$ ni topamiz. Bularni e'tiborga olsak, berilgan tenglamalar sistemasi quyidagi tenglamalar sistemasi teng kuchli bo'ladi:

$$\begin{cases} x + y = 5, \\ xy = 4 \end{cases}$$

Teoreмага asosan x va y lar $t^2 - 5t + 4 = 0$ kvadrat tenglamani ildizlari bo'ladi.

$$t_{1,2} = \frac{5 \pm \sqrt{25 - 16}}{2} = \frac{5 \pm 3}{2}, \quad t_1 = 1, \quad t_2 = 4$$

$$\text{Bulardan } \begin{cases} x_1 = 1 & x_2 = 4 \\ y_1 = 4 & y_2 = 1 \end{cases}$$

$$\text{Keying misollarda } \begin{cases} x + y = a \\ xy = b \end{cases}$$

ko'rinishidagi tenglamalar sistemasini yechimlarini keltirmasdan, faqat javoblarini keltiramiz.

$$\text{2-misol. } \begin{cases} x^5 + y^5 = 33 \\ x + y = 3 \end{cases} \text{ tenglamalar sistemasini yeching}$$

$\Delta\sigma_1 = x+y, \sigma_2 = xy$ deb, jadvaldan

$S_5 = x^5 + y^5 = \sigma_1^5 - 5\sigma_1^3\sigma_2 + 5\sigma_1\sigma_2^2$ tenglikni e'tiborga olsak, berilgan tenglamalar sistemasidan

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_1^5 - 5\sigma_1^3\sigma_2 + 5\sigma_1\sigma_2^2 = 33 \\ \sigma_1 = 3 \end{cases} \text{ tenglamalar sistemasiga ega bo'lamiz.}$$

Bundan σ_2 nisbatan

$$15\sigma_2^2 - 135\sigma_2 + 210 = 0, \quad \hat{=} \hat{=} \quad \sigma_2^2 - 9\sigma_2 + 14 = 0.$$

Bu kvadrat tenglamani $\sigma_1 = 2$ va $\sigma_2 = 7$ larni topamiz. Bularni e'tiborga olsak, berilgan tenglamalar sistemasi quyidagi ikkita sistemaga teng kuchli bo'ladi:

$$\begin{cases} x + y = 3 \\ xy = 2 \end{cases} \quad \hat{=} \hat{=} \quad \begin{cases} x + y = 3 \\ xy = 7 \end{cases}$$

Bu sistemalarni yechib, quyidagi javobga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\begin{cases} x_1 = 2 \\ y_1 = 1 \end{cases}, \begin{cases} x_2 = 1 \\ y_2 = 2 \end{cases}, \begin{cases} x_3 = \frac{3}{2} + \frac{\sqrt{19}}{2}i \\ y_3 = \frac{3}{2} - \frac{\sqrt{19}}{2}i \end{cases}, \begin{cases} x_4 = \frac{3}{2} - \frac{\sqrt{19}}{2}i \\ y_4 = \frac{3}{2} + \frac{\sqrt{19}}{2}i \end{cases}$$

3-misol. $\begin{cases} x^3 + y^3 = 8 \\ x^2 + y^2 = 4 \end{cases}$ tenglamalar sistemasini yeching.

Yuqoridagi misollardagi kabi $\sigma_1 = x+y$, $\sigma_2 = xy$ deb, berilgan tenglamalar sistemasini quyidagi sistemaga teng kuchli almashtiramiz:

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_1^3 - 3\sigma_1\sigma_2 = 8 \\ \sigma_1^2 - 2\sigma_2 = 4 \end{cases}$$
 bu sistemaning 2-tenglamasidan σ_2 ni topib, 2-tenglamasiga

qo'ysak, σ_1 nisbatan $\sigma_1^3 - 12\sigma_1 + 16 = 0$ tenglamaga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1^3 - 2\sigma_1^2 + 2\sigma_1^2 - 4\sigma_1 - 8\sigma_1 + 16 &= \sigma_1^3(\sigma_1 - 2) + 2\sigma_1(\sigma_1 - 2) - 8(\sigma_1 - 2) = \\ &= (\sigma_1 - 2)(\sigma_1^2 + 2\sigma_1 - 8) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Bundan $\sigma_1 - 2 = 0$ yoki $\sigma_1^2 + 2\sigma_1 - 8 = 0$ tenglamalarga ega bo'lamiz, bularni yechib $\sigma_1 = 2$, $\sigma_2 = -4$ larni topamiz. $\sigma_1 = 2$ bo'lganda $\sigma_2 = 0$ yoki $\sigma_1 = -4$ bo'lganda $\sigma_2 = 6$. Shunday qilib, berilgan, sistema quyidagi ikkita sistemaga teng kuchli:

$$\begin{cases} x + y = 2 \\ xy = 0 \end{cases}, \begin{cases} x + y = -4 \\ xy = 6 \end{cases}$$
 sistemalarni yechib, quyidagi 4 ta javobga ega

bo'lamiz: $\begin{cases} x_1 = 2 \\ y_1 = 0 \end{cases}, \begin{cases} x_2 = 0 \\ y_2 = 2 \end{cases}, \begin{cases} x_3 = -2 + i\sqrt{2} \\ y_3 = -2 - i\sqrt{2} \end{cases}, \begin{cases} x_4 = -2 - i\sqrt{2} \\ y_4 = -2 + i\sqrt{2} \end{cases}$

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

1. Sh.A. Ayupov, B.A. Omirov, A.X. Xudoyberdiyev, F.H. Haydarov, Algebra va sonlar nazariyasi, Toshkent "Tafakkur bo'stoni" 2019, 295 b.
2. Назаров Р.Н., Тошпўлатов Б.Т., Дусумбетов А.Д. Алгебра ва сонлар назарияси. Т., Ўқитувчи. I – қисм, 1993 й., II - қисм, 1995 й
3. В. Г. Болтянский, Н. Я. Виленкин. Симметрия в алгебре. М.: Наука, гл. ред. физ.мат. лит., 2002